

DTERBIM News

Insights on digital, circular and energy-efficient construction and renovation

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Dear reader,

In this edition, we introduce the people behind DTERBIM, share our latest updates, and bring you a selection of resources, events, and insights from across the construction and renovation sector.

Let's get started!

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Main story: [DTERBIM Voices](#) **The people, expertise and ideas driving our work**

Introducing: DTERBIM Voices

We have recently launched [DTERBIM Voices](#), a new interview series that puts a human face on the research and innovation behind our project.

Through conversations with our partners, we are highlighting the people, expertise, and ideas shaping DTERBIM's vision for a more digital, circular, and energy-efficient renovation.

Dimitrios Rovas, Professor of Building Simulation and Optimization at **University College London (UCL)**, explains how his team is helping establish the BIM-based process, data requirements and quality assurance methods that underpin DTERBIM. He also reflects on the importance of reliable, reusable building data for better renovation decisions and lifecycle management:

💬 *"The wider ambition is a built environment in which good data quality is the foundation for lower carbon, lower cost, and more circular renovation."*

Stathis Stamatopoulos, Researcher at the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), shares how his team is developing AI-driven tools that turn raw building data into actionable insights. From reducing energy consumption to supporting smarter design decisions before construction begins, these tools are helping unlock the full potential of Digital Twins and data-driven renovation:

💬 *"If five years from now a mid-sized building owner in Europe expects to operate their building with a Digital Twin the same way they expect to have heating, then DTERBIM will have made a real difference."*

👉 [Read Dimitrios' interview](#)

👉 [Read Stathis' interview](#)

Latest updates

9 July 2026: DTERBIM will join discussion on Digital Twins for climate-resilient cities

Green Deal Projects Support Office Webinar
9 July 2026

**"Smart Cities in Action:
Digital Twins, Real-time Data, AI, and
Mobility for Urban Climate Resilience"**

On 9 July 2026, we will participate in the Green Deal Projects Support Office (GD-SO) webinar, "**Smart Cities in Action: Digital Twins, Real-time Data, AI, and Mobility for Urban Climate Resilience.**"

Our coordinator, **Sonia Álvarez Díaz (CARTIF)**, will present DTERBIM alongside other Horizon Europe projects and representatives from European institutions, highlighting how Digital Twins, AI, and other data-driven technologies can support smarter, greener, and more resilient cities.

[Registration open until 7 July 2026](#) →

We participate in the 28th International Passive House Conference

Our partner, the **Hellenic Passive House Institute (HPHI)**, took to the stage at the **28th International Passive House Conference**, where researchers **Ilektra Mancini** and **Dimitris Pallantzas** presented a study on energy poverty in metropolitan cities.

The ongoing research combines district energy and comfort simulations with extensive fieldwork, including questionnaires, monitoring, energy studies, and thermography, across more than 100 buildings in Greece. The aim is to **calibrate digital modelling with real-time** data to build a more accurate picture of **how energy poverty manifests at the urban scale**.

At DTERBIM, we will contribute to the next stages of this research. Our **early design and assessment tools**, together with our **BIM models**, will help **guide decision-makers and policymakers**.

[Learn more](#) →

DTERBIM appears in the PTEC 2025 Projects Yearbook through partner CEMOSA

DTERBIM has been featured in the **Spanish Construction Technology Platform (PTEC) 2025 Projects Yearbook** through our partner CEMOSA. The publication showcases leading national and European initiatives advancing innovation across the construction sector.

It includes projects organised around **key thematic areas shaping the future of construction**, including digitalisation, sustainability, circularity, and energy **transition**. DTERBIM is among the European projects contributing to a more digital, interoperable, and resource-efficient built environment.

[Learn more](#) →

Highlights from our first periodic meeting in Brussels

Hosted by the **Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE)** on 28 and 29 April 2026, the meeting brought together representatives from our 18 partner organisations to review progress, address challenges, and align on our next steps.

The meeting offered a valuable opportunity to reflect on progress so far, clarify priorities for the months ahead, and reconnect in person while coordinating across technical and pilot activities.

[Learn more](#) →

Fresh news from the sector

White paper: Can innovation make construction more inclusive?

A new white paper from the [Tech4EUConstruction Cluster](#), which we are part of, explores **how emerging technologies can help address gender-related barriers in construction**. From robotics and exoskeletons to 3D printing and Digital Twins, the report highlights how innovation can reduce physical strain, improve safety, and open up more skill-based and digitally driven roles across the sector.

[Read the paper](#) →

Event: ReSBE 2026 (Thessaloniki, 20-23 October)

ReSBE 2026 is an international conference dedicated to **reshaping the built environment through sustainability and circularity**, bringing together researchers, practitioners, innovators, and policymakers to explore transformative solutions. Topics span circular design and construction, digitalisation, lifecycle assessment, climate adaptation, policy, and more. [Find out more](#) →

Report: Deloitte's 2026 Engineering and Construction Industry Outlook

Digital workflows integrating BIM, 3D printing, and Digital Twins are streamlining project delivery, enabling more accurate planning, reducing rework, and shortening project timelines by up to 20%. This is one of the findings from Deloitte's latest industry outlook, a report that maps the challenges and opportunities facing the construction sector. [Read the report](#) →

Reading for the summer: EEA briefing on circular economy and climate

The European Environment Agency recently published a briefing on the climate mitigation potential of circular economy actions, and the numbers for construction are striking. **Circular measures could reduce construction sector emissions by an average of 48%**, placing it among the sectors with the highest potential for circular climate mitigation. [Read the briefing](#) →

Thank you for being part of the DTERBIM community!

Together, we are helping advance a more digital, circular, and sustainable built environment.

The DTERBIM Team

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Your feedback is a gift to us!

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